

Icotrokinra as a selective IL-23 receptor inhibitor: a new oral therapeutic strategy in psoriasis

Adhurim Bresa¹

¹ Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Prishtina, Prishtina, Kosovo

² Department of Dermatology, Prizren Regional Hospital, Prizren, Kosovo

³ Institute and Comprehensive Center for Inflammation Medicine, University of Luebeck, Luebeck, Germany

Corresponding author: Diamant Thaçi (diamant.thaci@uksh.de)

Received 25 May 2026 ♦ Accepted 3 June 2026 ♦ Published 15 June 2026

Citation: Bresa A, Kastrati B, Berisha E, Besimi I, Thaçi D (2026) Icotrokinra as a selective IL-23 receptor inhibitor: a new oral therapeutic strategy in psoriasis. *Pharmacia* 73: e201064. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e201064>

Abstract

Background: Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin condition characterized by immune dysregulation, systemic manifestations, and a substantial impact on the overall quality of life of affected individuals. The IL-23/Th17 signaling pathway is a critical driver of psoriasis pathogenesis and has become a primary focus of targeted therapies. Injectable inhibitors of IL-23 and IL-17 have significantly improved clinical outcomes. More recently, the development of selective oral agents has introduced new possibilities for treatment accessibility and patient adherence.

Objective: This narrative review aims to examine the role of IL-23 in psoriasis pathophysiology and summarize the available pre-clinical and clinical evidence on approved IL-23 inhibitors and the emerging oral IL-23 receptor antagonist icotrokinra. In addition, indirect comparisons of efficacy and safety outcomes reported across published studies are discussed to provide clinical context.

Methods: A narrative review was conducted using literature retrieved from PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Peer-reviewed clinical trials, preclinical studies, review articles, and pharmacodynamic reports relevant to psoriasis, IL-23 signaling, and icotrokinra were evaluated. Efficacy was primarily assessed using PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 response rates.

Results: Available clinical evidence suggests that risankizumab and guselkumab achieve the highest PASI response rates, with durable efficacy and favorable safety profiles. Icotrokinra demonstrated dose-dependent efficacy, with the 100 mg regimen achieving PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 response rates of 65%, 51%, and 26%, respectively, at week 52. While the reported efficacy of icotrokinra was lower than that observed with risankizumab and guselkumab, it was generally comparable to that reported for tildrakizumab and ustekinumab. Icotrokinra was well tolerated, with no serious treatment-related adverse events reported.

Conclusion: IL-23 remains a validated and high-impact therapeutic target in psoriasis. Although injectable biologics currently offer superior efficacy, icotrokinra represents a promising oral alternative with a favorable safety profile and the potential to improve treatment accessibility. Its role in future treatment algorithms will depend on long-term data and real-world performance.

Keywords

Biologic therapy, guselkumab, icotrokinra, IL-23, IL-23 receptor, PASI response, psoriasis, risankizumab, Th17 cells

Introduction

Psoriasis is a common chronic inflammatory skin disorder driven by autoimmune processes and influenced by a strong hereditary component (Rendon and Schäkel 2019). Its development results from a complex interaction between genetic susceptibility and a range of environmental or internal triggers. The genetic component involves multiple genes, mainly those that regulate immune responses and drive skin inflammation (Chiricozzi et al. 2014).

Psoriasis affects approximately 2–3% of the global population, occurring more frequently in adults than in children (Estevinho et al. 2023). It is associated with several critical medical conditions, including depression, psoriatic arthritis, and cardiometabolic syndrome (Griffiths et al. 2021).

Recent research has shown that the immune system plays a significant role, particularly through two types of immune cells: Th1 and Th17 lymphocytes (Kutwin et al. 2021). These cells play a crucial role in driving the development of psoriatic lesions through specific immune pathways, including the IL-12/Th1/IFN- γ and IL-23/Th17/IL-17 pathways (Rivas Bejarano and Valdecantos 2013; Vičić et al. 2021).

Psoriasis is classified into several main types based on its appearance and location. The most common form, plaque psoriasis, accounts for 80–90% of cases and is characterized by erythematous plaques covered with silvery scales (Nestle et al. 2009; Boehncke and Schön 2015).

Guttate psoriasis presents as small red spots, often following streptococcal infections, and primarily affects children and young adults (Ko et al. 2010). Pustular psoriasis is characterized by white pustules on a red background and can be either localized or generalized (Navarini et al. 2017). Erythrodermic psoriasis is a severe, potentially life-threatening variant involving at least 75% of the skin surface. It is characterized by widespread redness and scaling and requires immediate medical intervention (Singh et al. 2016).

Psoriasis can usually be diagnosed relatively easily by the presence of characteristic red plaques with well-defined borders and dry, silvery-white scales. These typically appear on the elbows, knees, scalp, and lumbosacral area, although the condition can sometimes be more widespread (Perera et al. 2012; Lowes et al. 2014).

Individuals with psoriasis often report physical symptoms, including itching, skin flaking, and pain (de Korte et al. 2004). However, the impact extends beyond visible skin lesions. They frequently report physical discomfort, emotional strain, and struggles with negative body image or self-esteem issues (Finlay and Coles 1995; Augustin and Radtke 2014). This can affect their daily activities, from socializing to simple tasks such as work or activities that require exposing their skin (Kolli et al. 2018).

Over the past two decades, psoriasis has come to be recognized not only as a skin disorder but also as a complex, systemic disease driven by immune dysregulation (Dowlatshahi et al. 2013; Ten Bergen et al. 2020). Advances in molecular biology have led to the development of biologic treatments that precisely target key cytokines such

as tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α), IL-17, and IL-23, providing patients with more effective and personalized treatment options (Ten Bergen et al. 2020; Kutwin et al. 2021).

However, despite these advances, psoriasis remains a lifelong condition that can vary in severity and is often associated with other health issues. This highlights the ongoing need for research into the underlying causes of psoriasis and the best ways to manage it (Kolli et al. 2018; Loft et al. 2020).

IL-23 in psoriasis: structure, signaling, and pathogenic role

Interleukin-23 (IL-23) is a pro-inflammatory cytokine primarily produced by macrophages and antigen-presenting cells following antigenic stimulation. It plays a significant role in mediating tissue damage and is implicated in the pathogenesis of chronic inflammatory diseases (Korta et al. 2023).

IL-23 consists of two distinct protein subunits arranged as a heterodimer (Kutwin et al. 2021). The p19 subunit, exclusive to IL-23, forms a four-helix bundle and has a molecular weight of approximately 19 kDa. It is covalently linked via a disulfide bond to the p40 subunit, a 40 kDa component also found in IL-12, where it pairs with the p35 subunit instead (Oppmann et al. 2000; Lupardus and Garcia 2008; Chiricozzi et al. 2014).

IL-23 belongs to the IL-12 cytokine family, which is part of the broader IL-6 cytokine family (Duvall et al. 2011). The IL-12 receptor is composed of two chains, IL-12R β 1 and IL-12R β 2, which are homologous to the IL-6 receptor (Watford et al. 2004).

Activated myeloid cells, along with epithelial and endothelial cells, are the primary sources of IL-23. It signals through its receptor complex, which consists of two components: one component is unique to IL-23 (IL-23R), and the other component (IL-12R β 1) is shared with the receptor used by IL-12 (Parham et al. 2002; Di Meglio and Nestle 2010).

The interaction between IL-23R and its specific ligand, IL-23, activates a cascade of signals that influence the characteristics and activity of immune cells, playing a crucial role in regulating Th17 cells (Audia et al. 2024).

The IL-23R is expressed on a diverse array of cell types, including natural killer cells, macrophages, dendritic cells, memory T cells, and keratinocytes, highlighting its broad role in both innate and adaptive immune responses (Duvall et al. 2011; Fotiadou et al. 2018). This receptor is present on various immune cells, including Th17 cells, which play a central role in the pathogenesis of psoriasis (Kutwin et al. 2021).

In psoriasis, the IL-23R gene is highly upregulated on dermal dendritic cells and Langerhans cells, while IL-23 is overproduced by both dendritic cells and keratinocytes in lesions. In mice, nociceptors trigger IL-23 production by dermal dendritic cells, thereby promoting skin inflammation (Riol-Blanco et al. 2014; Girolomoni et al. 2017).

IL-23 is a key cytokine that regulates the development, function, and survival of Th17 cells. At the same time, IL-

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the immunopathogenesis of psoriasis and currently available targeted biologic therapies. Myeloid cells in the dermis and epidermis produce IL-12 and IL-23, which bind to their respective receptors (IL-12R β 1, IL-12R β 2, IL-23R) on naïve T cells. This activates Th17 cell differentiation, leading to the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-17A, IL-17F, IL-21, IL-22, and TNF- α . These cytokines contribute to epidermal hyperplasia and chronic inflammation, resulting in the formation of psoriatic plaques (Stritesky et al. 2008). Biologic therapies, such as ustekinumab, block both the IL-12 and IL-23 pathways (Yeilding et al. 2012). In contrast, agents such as guselkumab, risankizumab, and tildrakizumab specifically inhibit the IL-23 p19 subunit, whereas investigational icotrokinra targets the IL-23R, thereby targeting the IL-23/Th17 axis more selectively (Fourie et al. 2024; Huang et al. 2023), created with www.biorender.com.

17 and TNF contribute to the effector responses of both innate (TNF) and adaptive (TNF, IL-17) immune cells (Girolomoni et al. 2017; Bunte and Beikler 2019).

Th17 cells are a subset of T cells that produce pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-17, playing a crucial role in immune defense against pathogens while also contributing to the development of autoimmune and inflammatory diseases, including psoriasis (Oppmann et al. 2000; Aggarwal et al. 2003).

While IL-23 is not required for the initial differentiation of Th17 cells, it is essential for their activation, expansion, and maintenance (Chan et al. 2006). IL-23 binds to its receptor on Th17 cells, triggering signaling pathways that prevent apoptosis and promote the production of inflammatory cytokines, including IL-17A, IL-17F, IL-21, IL-22, and TNF, as shown in Fig. 1 (Stritesky et al. 2008).

Through this mechanism, IL-23 sustains and amplifies the inflammatory response of Th17 cells, thereby leading to chronic inflammation and tissue damage in diseases such as psoriasis (Bunte and Beikler 2019).

Approved IL-23 inhibitors: clinical evidence and mode of action

Currently, four monoclonal antibody therapies targeting the IL-23 pathway have been approved for the treatment of moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis (Zhou et al. 2021).

Biologic therapies targeting the IL-23 pathway represent an important treatment option for patients with

moderate-to-severe disease (Nakamura et al. 2017). Guselkumab, risankizumab, and tildrakizumab selectively bind to the p19 subunit of IL-23, thereby preventing its interaction with the IL-23R on Th17 cells and inhibiting downstream inflammatory signaling. In contrast, ustekinumab targets the shared p40 subunit of IL-12 and IL-23, thereby inhibiting both cytokine pathways. Through these mechanisms, IL-23 pathway-targeted therapies suppress Th17-mediated inflammatory responses and reduce the production of downstream pro-inflammatory cytokines, ultimately leading to decreased inflammation in psoriatic tissues (Huang et al. 2023).

Guselkumab

Guselkumab is a fully human IgG1 λ monoclonal antibody that binds with high affinity and specificity to the p19 subunit of IL-23, a cytokine involved in the pathogenesis of inflammatory diseases (Nakamura et al. 2017).

By selectively targeting this subunit, guselkumab effectively inhibits IL-23 activity and has been approved for the treatment of moderate-to-severe psoriasis (Mease et al. 2020).

Early-phase clinical trials (phases I and II) confirmed the safety and efficacy of this treatment in this indication (Sofen et al. 2014; Gordon et al. 2015). Moreover, results from a phase II study demonstrated that guselkumab significantly improved the clinical manifestations of active psoriatic arthritis and was well tolerated over 12 months of continuous treatment (Nakamura et al. 2017; Mease et al. 2020).

By binding to IL-23 with high affinity and specificity, guselkumab prevents the cytokine from interacting with its cell-surface receptor, thereby interrupting IL-23 signaling and reducing the production of downstream pro-inflammatory cytokines (Nogueira and Torres 2019).

Guselkumab has demonstrated a significant effect by reducing mRNA expression levels of IL-17F and IL-22, while increasing IFN- γ production by Th1 cells. These findings suggest that its clinical efficacy primarily stems from selective inhibition of the IL-23/Th17 pathway, without disrupting the IL-12/Th1 axis (Sofen et al. 2014; Nogueira and Torres 2019).

Phase III clinical trials have confirmed that guselkumab is a safe and effective treatment for moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis across a diverse patient population. More than 70% of patients achieved a PASI 90 response, indicating substantial clinical improvement and potential for enhanced quality of life. Notably, this response was maintained for a median duration of 15.2 weeks following treatment discontinuation (Nakamura et al. 2017; Zhou et al. 2021). Guselkumab shows a consistent safety profile, with the most common adverse effects being nasopharyngitis, headache, upper respiratory tract infections, and, less frequently, injection-site reactions, joint pain, itching, and back pain (Naik 2022).

Risankizumab

Risankizumab is a humanized monoclonal antibody of the IgG1 subclass that specifically targets the p19 subunit of IL-23. By binding to this subunit, it selectively inhibits IL-23 and reduces its pro-inflammatory activity (Banaszczyk 2019a).

Treatment with risankizumab has been shown to significantly reduce the expression of several key pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-17A, IL-17F, IL-21, and IL-22 (Gu and Yang 2019).

In a phase 1 clinical trial involving patients with moderate-to-severe psoriasis, risankizumab demonstrated rapid and sustained clearance of psoriatic skin lesions (Papp et al. 2017). In a phase 2 study, risankizumab demonstrated greater efficacy than ustekinumab, achieving faster and more sustained skin clearance, thereby emphasizing the importance of IL-23 in the pathogenesis of psoriasis (Papp et al. 2017; Gordon et al. 2018).

At week 12, a single dose of risankizumab resulted in a 75% reduction in PASI scores for 87% of patients, with 58% achieving a 90% improvement (Huang and Tsai 2020).

In phase III, four clinical trials were performed in which risankizumab demonstrated high efficacy in treating moderate-to-severe psoriasis, surpassing placebo, ustekinumab, and adalimumab in achieving PASI 90 and sPGA 0/1 responses by week 16, with sustained improvements up to week 52 (Gordon et al. 2018; Huang and Tsai 2020; Strober et al. 2020).

Risankizumab treatment improved health-related quality of life and was generally well tolerated during both short- and long-term treatment periods. Taken together,

these findings support the use of risankizumab as a valuable treatment option for patients with moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis (Blair 2020).

Risankizumab is generally safe and well tolerated, with common side effects including nasopharyngitis, respiratory infections, joint pain, headache, and hypertension. Rare but serious events, such as sepsis, pneumonia, and cardiovascular issues, have also been reported (Shu et al. 2023).

Tildrakizumab

Tildrakizumab is a humanized IgG1 kappa monoclonal antibody that selectively targets the p19 subunit of IL-23. By binding specifically to this subunit, it prevents IL-23 from interacting with its receptor, thereby inhibiting its biological activity (Sinclair and Thirthar Palanivelu 2019).

Tildrakizumab inhibits IL-23p19 binding to its receptor, thereby reducing IL-23 signaling. This leads to decreased activation of immune cells, such as Th17 cells, and lowers STAT3 activity, resulting in reduced production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-17A and IL-17F, as well as other mediators that contribute to the development of psoriatic plaques (Gaffen et al. 2014).

In all clinical trials, tildrakizumab demonstrated notable clinical improvement and a favorable safety profile. In phase III studies, 75% of patients treated with tildrakizumab achieved PASI 75 by week 28, demonstrating greater efficacy compared to etanercept (Bangert and Kopp 2018).

Tildrakizumab is a promising option for treating moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis, particularly in patients who have not responded well to other therapies. Its use in clinical practice may lead to improved outcomes for patients with difficult-to-manage disease. The most frequently reported side effects of tildrakizumab were headache and upper respiratory infections, with other common adverse events including injection-site hematomas (Banaszczyk 2019b).

Ustekinumab

Ustekinumab was shown to neutralize IL-12 by binding to its p40 subunit, thereby preventing IL-12 from binding to the β 1 chain of the IL-12 receptor complex. After the discovery of IL-23, ustekinumab was also found to inhibit IL-23 activity through a similar mechanism by binding to the shared p40 subunit and preventing its interaction with the β 1 chain of the IL-23 receptor complex.

The dual neutralization of IL-12 and IL-23 biological activity by ustekinumab is enabled by its ability to target the common p40 subunit shared by both cytokines (Yeilding et al. 2012).

Ustekinumab achieves its therapeutic efficacy by inhibiting the production of IL-12 and IL-23, resulting in reduced expression of skin-homing cell-surface markers, increased production of anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-5, and suppressed secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IFN- γ , IL-2, IL-8, IL-10, IL-17A, and TNF- α (Quatresooz et al. 2012).

Ustekinumab has proven to be highly effective and well tolerated in the treatment of patients with moderate-to-severe psoriasis (Reddy et al. 2010).

At week 12, PASI 75 was achieved by 67.1% of patients treated with 45 mg ustekinumab, 66.4% of patients treated with 90 mg ustekinumab, and only 3.1% of patients receiving placebo (Leonardi et al. 2008).

Across six trials, the most common side effects of ustekinumab included headache, upper respiratory infections, and nasopharyngitis. Serious events such as infections, cardiovascular issues, and malignancies were rare. No significant differences in adverse effects were found between dosage groups or compared to placebo, except for a higher infection rate in the 45 mg group (Naik 2022).

Review methodology

This narrative review was conducted through a literature search of PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar up to March 2025. Search terms included “psoriasis,” “IL-23,” “IL-23 receptor,” “icotrokinra,” “JNJ-77242113,” “guselkumab,” “risankizumab,” “tildrakizumab,” “ustekinumab,” and “IL-17 inhibitors.” Relevant clinical trials, review articles, preclinical studies, and pharmacodynamic investigations were considered. Additional information was obtained from publicly available clinical trial registries and conference reports where appropriate. Studies were selected based on their relevance to psoriasis pathophysiology, the IL-23/Th17 pathway, and the clinical development of icotrokinra.

IL-17 in psoriasis: immunological role and therapeutic relevance

The activation and expansion of CD4⁺ T cells lead to their differentiation into various helper T-cell types, each with distinct cytokine profiles and specific roles within the immune response. For a long time, these T cells were thought to be either Th1 or Th2, based on the cytokines they produce (Korn et al. 2009; Zhu et al. 2010).

However, more recently, a third group of cells, known as Th17 cells, has been identified, which produce a unique set of cytokines, including IL-17, IL-17F, and IL-22 (Miossec and Kolls 2012).

Interleukin-17 (IL-17) is a promising target for biologic treatments, playing a crucial role in immune-related diseases. Th17 cells play a vital role in regulating both adaptive and innate immune responses (Miossec and Kolls 2012; Hohenberger et al. 2018). IL-17A affects a variety of cell types, including neutrophils, lymphocytes, macrophages, fibroblasts, keratinocytes, epithelial cells, endothelial cells, and dendritic cells (van den Berg and McInnes 2013).

IL-17A plays a vital role in defending the body against bacterial and fungal infections. Increasing evidence also implicates IL-17A as a key contributor to the pathogenesis of psoriasis (Girolomoni et al. 2012). Genetic defects in IL17RA and IL-17A may result in excessive colonization of *Candida*

albicans in the gastrointestinal tract, potentially leading to inflammation (Colombel et al. 2013; Hohenberger et al. 2018).

Comparison of IL-17 inhibitors: secukinumab, ixekizumab, and bimekizumab

IL-17 inhibitors represent a newer class of biologic therapies that provide more precise targeting in the treatment of psoriasis (Bilal et al. 2018). Patients receiving IL-17 inhibitors often achieve clinical outcomes comparable to or exceeding those observed with other currently available biologic agents (Chiricozzi and Krueger 2013; Amin et al. 2018).

These drugs also have a good short-term safety record. Phase III clinical trial results demonstrate that IL-17 inhibitors are highly effective therapeutic options for individuals with psoriasis (Chiricozzi and Krueger 2013). Here, the findings from trials of three IL-17 inhibitors are examined: secukinumab, ixekizumab, and bimekizumab (Ly et al. 2019).

Secukinumab, a fully human monoclonal antibody that blocks the inflammatory cytokine IL-17A, has demonstrated strong efficacy and a favorable safety profile in treating moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis (Langley et al. 2014; Bissonnette et al. 2017; Reich, Puig et al. 2020). Treatment with subcutaneous secukinumab, administered as three 75 mg injections and three 150 mg injections, met the primary endpoint of a 75% improvement in psoriasis severity (PASI 75) after 12 weeks, demonstrating its effectiveness for moderate-to-severe psoriasis (Papp et al. 2013; Rich et al. 2013).

Additionally, secukinumab may act by directly modulating the role of IL-17 in promoting neutrophil survival and activation, as shown in earlier studies (Reich et al. 2015; Bilal et al. 2018).

Ixekizumab is a biologic medicine approved for the treatment of moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis. It is a humanized monoclonal antibody that targets IL-17A and is administered as a subcutaneous injection (Syed 2017; Craig and Warren 2020).

By week 12, the percentage of patients achieving a 75% improvement from baseline psoriasis severity (PASI 75) was comparable among the three phase III trials (Farahnik et al. 2016). The most common side effects included sore throat, upper respiratory infections, and reactions at the injection site (Ruggiero et al. 2022).

Bimekizumab is a monoclonal IgG1 antibody that specifically blocks IL-17A and IL-17F (Gordon et al. 2021; Reich et al. 2021). It was recently approved for the treatment of moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis in adults eligible for systemic therapy (Ruggiero, Potestio et al. 2022).

Across all phase 3 trials, bimekizumab was generally well tolerated and had a safety profile similar to that of other biologic treatments. However, it was associated with a higher rate of oral yeast infections (oral candidiasis) (Freitas et al. 2021). At week 16, 85.5% of patients treated with bimekizumab (319 patients) achieved a PASI 90 response, meaning a 90% improvement in psoriasis symptoms (Ruggiero et al. 2022).

Figure 2. Chemical structure of icotrokinra, a synthetic macrocyclic peptide that acts as a selective IL-23R antagonist (Fourie et al. 2024), created with www.biorender.com.

Icotrokinra: a novel oral IL-23 receptor inhibitor

The IL-23 pathway plays a central role in promoting inflammation in conditions such as psoriasis, psoriatic arthritis, and other immune-mediated inflammatory diseases (Torti and Feldman 2007). Icotrokinra (formerly JNJ-77242113) is a novel oral peptide therapy designed to selectively and potently inhibit the IL-23R (Stein Gold et al. 2025).

Icotrokinra demonstrated potent and selective inhibition of proximal IL-23 signaling, with an IC₅₀ of 5.6 pM, while sparing IL-12 signaling. The compound also inhibited IL-23-stimulated interferon- γ (IFN- γ) production in natural killer cells and in blood samples from healthy donors and patients with psoriasis, with IC₅₀ values of 18.4 pM, 11 pM, and 9 pM, respectively, for each condition in that order.

Currently, there are no oral medications that specifically target this pathway. Icotrokinra is a peptide that binds to IL-23R with high affinity, effectively blocking IL-23 signaling in human T cells (Fourie et al. 2024). It also inhibits the production of IL-23-induced cytokines in human natural killer cells in a concentration-dependent manner, demonstrating high potency and targeted immunomodulatory activity (Fourie et al. 2023).

Icotrokinra is a synthetic macrocyclic peptide with a molecular weight of approximately 1898.19 g/mol. Its chemical structure is presented in Fig. 2 (Fourie et al. 2024).

Icotrokinra was generally well tolerated in healthy volunteers following both single- and multiple-dose regimens. In a recent phase II trial involving patients with moderate-to-severe psoriasis, the drug met its primary efficacy endpoint. It exhibited a safety profile comparable to that of placebo (Fourie et al. 2024).

The most frequently reported adverse events were mild to moderate in intensity and included COVID-19 infections, nasopharyngitis, and upper respiratory tract infections (Ferris et al. 2025; Rosenberg et al. 2025).

No serious cardiovascular events, cancers, or deaths were reported during the trial. However, larger and longer studies will be necessary to fully evaluate the risk of rare adverse effects. There was no apparent association between icotrokinra dose and the occurrence of adverse events (Bissonnette et al. 2024).

Icotrokinra exhibits low passive permeability, resulting in poor absorption. However, it does not interact with P-glycoprotein, meaning it is neither a substrate nor an inhibitor of this transporter (Bissonnette et al. 2024).

In vitro characterization of the mechanism of action and cytokine modulation

To explore the pharmacological properties of icotrokinra, a series of *in vitro* studies was conducted to assess its mechanism of action and effects on cytokine production.

Icotrokinra was shown to potently and selectively block IL-23-induced signaling (see Table 1) in human immune cells and whole blood. In peripheral blood mononuclear cells, it inhibited STAT3 phosphorylation in response to IL-23, with an IC₅₀ of 5.6 pM (Fourie et al. 2024).

When rat colon tissue samples were treated with JNJ-2100 in the laboratory, a dose-dependent decrease in IL-22 levels was observed, indicating that higher doses yielded more potent effects. Specifically, rat colon samples exposed to increasing doses (0.3, 3, and 30 mg/kg) showed reductions of 52%, 88%, and 96% in IL-22, respectively, compared to samples treated without the drug. Similarly, human colon tissue tested in the laboratory with JNJ-2100 or icotrokinra also showed a substantial, dose-related decrease in IL-22, with a reduction of more than 90% at the highest doses (Drucker 2020).

This selectivity was similar to that of anti-IL-23p19 antibodies, whereas anti-IL-23p40 antibodies blocked both the IL-23 and IL-12 pathways. These findings highlight the compound's strong specificity and mechanism of action at low concentrations.

To further evaluate the target specificity of icotrokinra for IL-23R, a broad panel of secondary pharmacological targets, including receptors, ion channels, enzymes, and transporters, was screened for potential off-target activity. At a concentration of 10 μ M, icotrokinra exhibited less than 50% inhibition or activation across all tested targets, supporting its high selectivity for IL-23R (Fourie et al. 2024).

In vivo pharmacodynamics, safety, and toxicology profile of icotrokinra

In addition to *in vitro* studies, *in vivo* experiments have been conducted to evaluate the safety and efficacy of icotrokinra.

To investigate systemic activity, rats were administered various oral doses of icotrokinra. Blood samples were subsequently collected and stimulated *ex vivo* with IL-23 and IL-1 β . The drug reduced IL-17A production in a clear, dose-dependent manner, with measurable effects observed at doses of 3 mg/kg and above (Fourie et al. 2024).

When administered orally, icotrokinra did not cause any treatment-related side effects in animal safety studies.

Table 1. Summary of preclinical and clinical data for JNJ-77242113 (icotrokinra). The table presents *in vitro* binding and functional activity, *in vivo* exposure in rats, and pharmacokinetic and safety data from human studies. Icotrokinra demonstrated high affinity for its target, adequate systemic exposure relative to its IC50, and was well tolerated across clinical phases (Fourie et al. 2024). Phase I data are reported by Fourie et al. (2024), phase II by Ferris et al. (2025), and phase III by Rosenberg et al. (2025).

	<i>In vitro</i> studies			<i>In vivo</i> studies		
	in rats			in rats		
	Binding affinity	MAO	IC50	Half-time	Adverse effects	Bioavailability
KD of 17.5 pM at 37 °C	Anti-IL-23p19/p40 antibodies when examining IL-23-induced pSTAT4 and IL-12-induced pSTAT3	250 ± 62 pM (at 20 ng/mL IL-23), 54 ± 34 pM (at 4 ng/mL IL-23)	2 hours (Tmax) after 10 mg/kg dose	Not reported in detail in rodents; no toxicity data shown	Low oral bioavailability; higher drug concentrations in GI tissue vs plasma	660 pM (above IC50 of 250 pM for IL-17A inhibition in whole blood)
	Studies in humans					
Dose	Cmax (µg/mL)	AUC0-∞ (µg*day/mL)	t1/2	Adverse effects		
				Phase I	Phase II	Phase III
10–1000 mg oral	0.7 ± 1.6	0.9 ± 1.5	9–16 h	No serious AEs or deaths related to JNJ-77242113 were reported, and no dose-related trends were observed. Treatment-related AEs were more frequent with JNJ-77242113 (31%) than placebo (20%), with headache being most common (10.3%).	Common AEs: Nasopharyngitis (18%), URTI (10%), COVID-19 (5%), GI AEs (11%) Serious AEs (≤1 case each): Coronary artery disease, noncardiac chest pain, ventricular dysfunction, foot deformity, disc protrusion, diverticulitis.	Nasopharyngitis, upper respiratory tract infection, COVID-19 infection (16 wk) 100 mg twice daily

In tests on cynomolgus monkeys (up to 300 mg/kg), no adverse effects on heart function were observed, and in rats (up to 600 mg/kg), no issues were noted with breathing or behavior. Icotrokinra did not show any signs of causing genetic damage in safety tests, including the bacterial reverse mutation test (Bissonnette et al. 2024).

In repeated-dose studies in rats, icotrokinra was well tolerated, with no signs of toxic effects (as summarized in Table 1) at oral doses up to 1000 mg/kg per day for 7 days (non-GLP), 600 mg/kg per day for 14 days (GLP), 70 mg/kg per day for 6 weeks (GLP), and 20 mg/kg per day for 4 months (GLP). In each case, the highest dose tested was considered the no-observed-adverse-effect level (NOAEL). In the 2-week study, blood drug levels (measured by AUC) increased significantly over time, reaching 5- to 47-fold higher by day 14 than on day 1. With longer treatment, drug accumulation continued, reaching up to 300 times higher after 6 weeks and up to 206 times higher after 4 months (Bissonnette et al. 2024).

In a rat model of skin inflammation, injecting IL-23 directly into the right ear led to a significant increase in the expression of specific genes, including those encoding IL-17A, IL-17F, and IL-22. These gene levels increased by more than 16-fold for IL-17A and by more than 100-fold for both IL-17F and IL-22 compared with ears injected with saline alone (Fourie et al. 2024).

In studies with rabbits, icotrokinra caused some maternal toxicity, leading to abortions in two females on gestation day 26. Additionally, at a dose of 500 mg/kg, there was a slight increase in the number of fetuses with fused ribs—an observation slightly above typical background levels seen in historical control data (Bissonnette et al. 2024).

In an *ex vivo* setting, a single 10 mg dose of icotrokinra reduced IL-23-induced IFN-γ production compared with placebo. A more substantial effect was observed with a 1000 mg dose, which completely suppressed IL-23-dependent IFN-γ production for up to 24 h after administration (Fourie et al. 2024). The pharmacological profile of icotrokinra across preclinical and early clinical phases is provided in Table 1.

Clinical evaluation of icotrokinra in humans

Following promising preclinical results, icotrokinra advanced to early clinical trials to evaluate its pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and safety in humans.

A first-in-human study of icotrokinra enrolled 95 healthy participants to assess its pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics across single- and multiple-ascending-dose arms. Plasma exposure increased proportionally with doses ranging from 10 to 1000 mg, with an estimated half-life of 9–16 h (Fourie et al. 2024).

In the multiple-dose phase, daily dosing led to modest drug accumulation, consistent with its half-life. Pharmacodynamic analysis showed dose-dependent inhibition of IL-23-induced IFN-γ production in whole blood, with complete inhibition observed at the 1000 mg dose for up to 24 h (de Leon-Tabaldo et al. 2024; Ferris et al. 2025). Overall, icotrokinra demonstrated favorable pharmacokinetics and apparent pharmacodynamic activity in humans (Fourie et al. 2024).

Only a few clinical trials have explored the potential of oral small molecules for treating psoriasis. These molecules can function by entering immune cells and blocking key inflammatory processes, such as T-cell activation, leukocyte movement, and the production of inflammatory mediators, while also promoting cell death where necessary (Rosenberg et al. 2025). Oral treatments hold promise for more accessible and convenient psoriasis care, but their safety and effectiveness still require thorough testing (Bissonnette et al. 2024).

The clinical improvements and patient-reported benefits observed with icotrokinra at week 16 were maintained over time, with no new safety concerns detected during up to 1 year of treatment. This study demonstrates that individuals with moderate-to-severe psoriasis can achieve lasting, significant improvements and a favorable safety profile with an oral, targeted IL-23R inhibitor (Ferris et al. 2025).

After 16 weeks of once- or twice-daily icotrokinra, patients with moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis experienced

Figure 3. Timeline of the translational development of icotrokinra, a selective small-molecule IL-23R antagonist (Stein Gold et al. 2025). The figure outlines key milestones from the identification of IL-23 as a central cytokine in autoimmune diseases through the design and preclinical validation of icotrokinra to its clinical evaluation. It includes significant steps, such as pharmacodynamic confirmation in humans. Promising phase 2 results in psoriasis have led to ongoing phase 3 trials (Ferris et al. 2025), created with www.biorender.com.

significantly better results than those receiving placebo. This oral medication, which blocks the IL-23R, has been shown to reduce psoriasis symptoms and demonstrates promise as an effective treatment option (de Leon-Tabaldo et al. 2024).

Ictrokinra stands out for its strong safety profile and is already in phase III trials; it is generally well tolerated, with no deaths or serious adverse events reported (Bissonnette et al. 2024; Rosenberg et al. 2025). In healthy volunteers, icotrokinra was well tolerated after both single and multiple doses. Reported adverse events were mild to moderate in severity, with no clear dose-related pattern. In addition to these findings, the safety profiles of monoclonal antibodies targeting IL-23 further support the potential of selectively modulating the IL-23 pathway as a viable therapeutic approach (Fourie et al. 2024).

Most patients (89%) from the FRONTIER-1 study continued into the FRONTIER-2 study. Response rates remained steady from week 16 to week 52, with the best results seen at a 100 mg twice-daily dose of icotrokinra. By week 52, 76% of patients achieved at least a 75% improvement in their psoriasis (PASI 75), and a significant number showed almost clear or clear skin.

Approximately 59% of patients experienced adverse events, but serious side effects were rare (4%) and not linked to the treatment. Overall, icotrokinra demonstrated encouraging safety and efficacy results, highlighting its potential as a convenient, targeted, and well-tolerated oral treatment option for psoriasis. This developmental journey is illustrated in Fig. 3, which outlines the translational progress of icotrokinra from early discovery through clinical validation (Ferris et al. 2025).

Comparative efficacy of icotrokinra and IL-23 inhibitors based on PASI 75, 90, and 100 response rates

Direct head-to-head clinical trials comparing icotrokinra with currently approved biologic therapies are currently unavailable. Therefore, the efficacy comparisons presented

in this review are based on indirect comparisons across separate clinical studies that differ in patient populations, study designs, treatment regimens, sample sizes, follow-up durations, and assessment time points. Consequently, these comparisons should be interpreted with caution and are intended to provide general clinical context rather than definitive comparative evidence.

A comparative assessment of biologic therapies for moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis highlights varying degrees of efficacy in achieving skin clearance. Among these therapies, icotrokinra, an investigational agent, is evaluated alongside approved IL-23 inhibitors (risankizumab, guselkumab, and tildrakizumab) and the IL-12/23 inhibitor ustekinumab, with a focus on PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 response rates.

Figure 4 illustrates differences in clinical performance among these agents at multiple time points, using data extracted from published clinical studies. The figure provides a visual summary of each drug's ability to achieve partial to complete skin clearance, which serves as the basis for the following interpretation.

PASI 75 response rate—The first bar graph (Fig. 4) illustrates the proportion of patients achieving PASI 75 at multiple time points (weeks 12, 16, 48, and 52) across five biologic therapies: JNJ-77242113, risankizumab, tildrakizumab, guselkumab, and ustekinumab.

Ictrokinra at a dose of 100 mg achieved a PASI 75 response rate of approximately 65% at week 16 ($n = 43$) (Bissonnette et al. 2024), which was maintained through week 52 (65%, $n = 43$) (Ferris et al. 2025).

In contrast, risankizumab 180 mg demonstrated superior efficacy, with 86% of patients achieving PASI 75 by week 16 ($n = 57$) (Hansel et al. 2021), and this rate increased further to 96.4% at week 52 ($n = 55$) (Hansel et al. 2022). Guselkumab 100 mg also showed consistently high responses, with 86.3% at week 16 ($n = 496$) (Blauvelt et al. 2017) and 87.8% at week 48 ($n = 329$) (Huang et al. 2023).

Tildrakizumab 100 mg demonstrated more modest efficacy, with response rates of 62.3% at week 12 ($n = 705$) (Papp et al. 2019) and 64.8% at week 52 ($n = 411$) (Reich et al. 2020),

Figure 4. PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 response rates over time for icotrokinra and comparator biologics. Data were extracted from independent clinical studies and are presented for descriptive purposes only. Direct efficacy comparisons should be interpreted with caution because of differences in study designs, patient populations, treatment regimens, and assessment time points.

closely resembling the profile of icotrokinra. Ustekinumab 90 mg exhibited a strong early response (75.7% at week 12, $n = 411$) (Papp et al. 2008) and maintained efficacy through week 28 (78.5%, $n = 400$) (Papp et al. 2008).

Overall, icotrokinra exhibited moderate efficacy in achieving PASI 75, with no observed increase beyond week 16. Risankizumab and guselkumab consistently outperformed other agents, while ustekinumab maintained stable yet superior early responses. Only tildrakizumab demonstrated a comparable efficacy profile to icotrokinra.

PASI 90 response rates—The second graph (Fig. 4) presents the percentage of patients achieving PASI 90 at key clinical time points (weeks 12, 16, 28, 48, and 52) for the same five agents.

Icotrokinra achieved a PASI 90 response rate of 47.0% at week 16 ($n = 43$) (Bissonnette et al. 2024), increasing slightly to 51.0% at week 52 ($n = 43$) (Ferris et al. 2025).

Although the early response was encouraging, data gaps beyond week 16 limit conclusions regarding durability between weeks 16 and 52.

Risankizumab demonstrated robust and sustained efficacy, with 63.2% of patients achieving PASI 90 by week 16 ($n = 57$) (Hansel et al. 2021) and 85.5% by week 52 ($n = 55$) (Hansel et al. 2022).

Guselkumab reached 70.0% at week 16 ($n = 496$) (Blauvelt et al. 2017), with a modest increase to 76.3% at week 48 ($n = 329$) (Huang et al. 2023). Tildrakizumab exhibited limited efficacy, with PASI 90 responses of 35.9% at week 12 ($n = 705$) (Papp et al. 2019) and 32.3% at week 52 ($n = 317$) (Reich et al. 2020).

Ustekinumab demonstrated stable efficacy, achieving 50.9% at week 12 ($n = 411$) and 54.3% at week 28 ($n = 400$) (Papp et al. 2008), results similar to those of icotrokinra.

Figure 5. Therapeutic efficacy of icotrokinra across three dosing regimens (25 mg, 50 mg, and 100 mg) compared with placebo, based on the proportion of patients achieving PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 responses at weeks 16 and 52. The figure illustrates both early and sustained clinical responses and highlights the dose-dependent efficacy observed across multiple treatment endpoints.

These findings highlight the superior efficacy of risankizumab and guselkumab in achieving greater disease control. While icotrokinra showed potential for early PASI 90 response, its long-term performance remains uncertain and requires further clinical validation.

PASI 100 response rates—The third bar graph (Fig. 4) presents response rates for complete skin clearance (PASI 100) at weeks 12, 16, 48, and 52, reflecting the most stringent therapeutic benchmark in psoriasis treatment.

Icotrokinra (100 mg) achieved PASI 100 responses of 23.0% at week 16 (Bissonnette et al. 2024) and 26.0% at week 52 ($n = 43$) (Ferris et al. 2025), indicating modest but sustained clinical improvement.

Risankizumab (180 mg) recorded the highest response rates among all agents, with 49.1% at week 16 ($n = 57$) (Hansel et al. 2021) and a peak of 60.0% at week 52 ($n = 55$) (Hansel et al. 2022), demonstrating both early and durable efficacy.

Guselkumab (100 mg) achieved PASI 100 responses of 34.1% at week 16 ($n = 496$) (Blauvelt et al. 2017) and 47.4% at week 48 ($n = 329$) (Huang et al. 2023), confirming its consistent performance over time.

Tildrakizumab (100 mg) showed the lowest PASI 100 responses in this comparison, rising from 13.2% at week 12 (Papp et al. 2019) to 20.0% at week 52 ($n = 411$) (Reich et al. 2020), suggesting limited efficacy in achieving full clearance.

Ustekinumab (90 mg) demonstrated minimal change, with 18.2% at week 12 ($n = 411$) and 29.5% at week 28 ($n = 400$) (Papp et al. 2008), indicating an early plateau.

These findings position risankizumab and guselkumab as the most effective biologics in achieving complete skin clearance within the observed time frame. Icotrokinra exhibited intermediate efficacy, while tildrakizumab and ustekinumab remained less effective based on PASI 100 outcomes.

Figure 5 illustrates the dose-dependent efficacy of icotrokinra across PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 endpoints at weeks 16 and 52.

At week 16, PASI 75 responses increased in a dose-dependent manner: 37% for 25 mg, 58% for 50 mg, and 65% for 100 mg, compared to 9% in the placebo group. Similar trends were observed for PASI 90 (26%, 51%, and 47%) and PASI 100 (12%, 26%, and 23%) across the same dose range. The placebo group showed minimal responses across all endpoints, confirming the treatment effect (Bissonnette et al. 2024).

By week 52, improvements were sustained or enhanced across all endpoints. PASI 75 responses were 49% (25 mg), 70% (50 mg), and 65% (100 mg), with placebo remaining constant at 66% (this may reflect a control or open-label continuation). PASI 90 responses reached 28%, 42%, and 51%, respectively, while PASI 100 responses rose to 14%, 21%, and 26%, indicating improved long-term efficacy, particularly at the 100 mg dose (Ferris et al. 2025).

These findings suggest a clear dose-response relationship, with icotrokinra demonstrating increasing efficacy with higher doses, particularly evident at week 52. The 100 mg dose appears to achieve the most consistent improvements across all PASI thresholds. The stable and low response rates in the placebo group fur-

ther support the therapeutic potential of icotrokinra in moderate-to-severe psoriasis. Icotrokinra has shown moderate but consistent efficacy across PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 endpoints, with the 100 mg dose producing the most favorable outcomes at week 52. Although it does not match the high response rates achieved by agents such as risankizumab and guselkumab, its clinical performance aligns closely with that of tildrakizumab and ustekinumab, particularly at higher clearance thresholds. The observed dose-dependent response and sustained efficacy over time suggest that icotrokinra may be a promising addition to the therapeutic arsenal for moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis.

Strengths and limitations of the study

This review provides a comprehensive synthesis of the current scientific understanding of psoriasis, with a particular focus on the IL-23/Th17 axis and the development of targeted therapies aimed at this pathway. A significant strength of the study lies in its integrative approach, which combines molecular, preclinical, and clinical data into a coherent, structured narrative. The inclusion of direct comparisons between established biologic agents and the emerging oral therapy, icotrokinra, enhances the practical relevance of the analysis, offering a realistic appraisal of how this new treatment may fit within the current therapeutic landscape. Furthermore, the emphasis on oral therapy reflects an essential shift in the field toward more accessible and patient-friendly treatment modalities.

However, this study is not without limitations. First, it is a narrative review that relies entirely on previously published data and does not conduct new statistical analyses or a formal meta-analysis. Second, the efficacy comparisons are drawn from clinical trials with varying designs, sample sizes, durations, and inclusion criteria, which limits the accuracy of direct cross-trial comparisons.

Furthermore, because the efficacy data were derived from independent clinical trials rather than direct head-to-head studies, no formal conclusions regarding superiority, non-inferiority, or comparative effectiveness between treatments can be established. Another limitation is the lack of long-term data on icotrokinra, which remains in the early stages of clinical development; its

long-term safety, durability of response, and comparative effectiveness are still uncertain. Lastly, the review focuses narrowly on the IL-23/IL-17 axis. It does not address other emerging therapeutic strategies, such as IL-36 inhibition, JAK inhibitors, or combination therapies, which may be relevant in cases of psoriasis that are resistant or complex.

Conclusion

Psoriasis is a chronic, immune-mediated skin disease with systemic implications and a significant burden on patient quality of life. Central to its pathogenesis is the dysregulation of the IL-23/Th17 axis, particularly involving key cytokines such as IL-23, IL-17A, and IL-17F, as well as downstream inflammatory mediators. Advances in immunology have shifted the treatment paradigm from broad immunosuppression to targeted biologics, with IL-23 and IL-17 inhibitors offering higher efficacy, longer-lasting disease control, and improved safety profiles.

Among IL-23 inhibitors, risankizumab and guselkumab consistently demonstrate superior efficacy across PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 benchmarks, maintaining durable responses over 52 weeks. Tildrakizumab and ustekinumab, while effective, show lower peak responses and flatter efficacy curves, particularly at higher clearance thresholds.

Icotrokinra, a novel oral IL-23R antagonist, represents a significant step forward in psoriasis therapy. Although its PASI 75, PASI 90, and PASI 100 responses do not yet match the top-performing injectables, its oral administration, target selectivity, and favorable safety profile make it a viable alternative, especially for patients who prefer or require non-injectable options. Phase II data show dose-dependent efficacy, with the 100 mg regimen yielding the most promising sustained clinical benefit.

In sum, IL-23 remains a validated and high-yield therapeutic target. While monoclonal antibodies continue to lead in efficacy, oral agents such as icotrokinra represent a new therapeutic class that could redefine treatment accessibility and patient adherence for moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis. Ongoing phase III data will determine its place in clinical practice, but the compound shows clear potential as a convenient, targeted, and well-tolerated treatment.

References

- Aggarwal S, Ghilardi N, Xie MH, de Sauvage FJ, Gurney AL (2003) Interleukin-23 promotes a distinct CD4 T cell activation state characterized by the production of interleukin-17. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry* 278(3): 1910–1914. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M207577200>
- Amin M, Darji K, No DJ, Bhutani T, Wu JJ (2018) Review of IL-17 inhibitors for psoriasis. *Journal of Dermatological Treatment* 29(4): 347–352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546634.2017.1395796>
- Audia S, Brescia C, Dattilo V, Torchia N, Trapasso F, Amato R (2024) The IL-23R and its genetic variants: A hitherto unforeseen bridge between the immune system and cancer development. *Cancers* 17(1): 55. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers17010055>
- Augustin M, Radtke MA (2014) Quality of life in psoriasis patients. *Expert Review of Pharmacoeconomics & Outcomes Research* 14(4): 559–568. <https://doi.org/10.1586/14737167.2014.914437>
- Banaszczyk K (2019a) Risankizumab in the treatment of psoriasis - literature review. *Reumatologia* 57(3): 158–162. <https://doi.org/10.5114/reum.2019.86426>
- Banaszczyk K (2019b) Tildrakizumab in the treatment of psoriasis - literature review. *Reumatologia* 57(4): 234–238. <https://doi.org/10.5114/reum.2019.87620>
- Bangert C, Kopp T (2018) Tildrakizumab for the treatment of psoriasis. *Immunotherapy* 10(13): 1105–1122. <https://doi.org/10.2217/imt-2018-0028>

- Bilal J, Berlinberg A, Bhattacharjee S, Trost J, Riaz IB, Kurtzman DJB (2018) A systematic review and meta-analysis of the efficacy and safety of the interleukin (IL)-12/23 and IL-17 inhibitors ustekinumab, secukinumab, ixekizumab, brodalumab, guselkumab and til-drakizumab for the treatment of moderate to severe plaque psoriasis. *Journal of Dermatological Treatment* 29(6): 569–578. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546634.2017.1422591>
- Bissonnette R, Luger T, Thaçi D, Toth D, Messina I, You R, Guana A, Fox T, Papavassilis C, Gilloteau I, Mrowietz U (2017) Secukinumab sustains good efficacy and favourable safety in moderate-to-severe psoriasis after up to 3 years of treatment: results from a double-blind extension study. *British Journal of Dermatology* 177(4): 1033–1042. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.15706>
- Bissonnette R, Pinter A, Ferris LK, Gerdes S, Rich P, Vender R, Miller M, Shen YK, Kannan A, Li S, DeKlotz C, Papp K (2024) An oral interleukin-23-receptor antagonist peptide for plaque psoriasis. *New England Journal of Medicine* 390(6): 510–521. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2308713>
- Blair HA (2020) Risankizumab: A review in moderate to severe plaque psoriasis. *Drugs* 80(12): 1235–1245. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40265-020-01357-1>
- Blauvelt A, Papp KA, Griffiths CEM, Randazzo B, Wasfi Y, Shen YK, Li S, Kimball AB (2017) Efficacy and safety of guselkumab, an anti-interleukin-23 monoclonal antibody, compared with adalimumab for the continuous treatment of patients with moderate to severe psoriasis: Results from the phase III, double-blinded, placebo- and active comparator-controlled VOYAGE 1 trial. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology* 76(3): 405–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2016.11.041>
- Boehncke WH, Schön MP (2015) Psoriasis. *Lancet* 386(9997): 983–994. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(14\)61909-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(14)61909-7)
- Bunte K, Beikler T (2019) Th17 Cells and the IL-23/IL-17 axis in the pathogenesis of periodontitis and immune-mediated inflammatory diseases. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 20(14): 3394. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20143394>
- Chan JR, Blumenschein W, Murphy E, Diveu C, Wiekowski M, Abbondanzo S, Lucian L, Geissler R, Brodie S, Kimball AB, Gorman DM, Smith K, de Waal Malefyt R, Kastelein RA, McClanahan TK, Bowman EP (2006) IL-23 stimulates epidermal hyperplasia via TNF and IL-20R2-dependent mechanisms with implications for psoriasis pathogenesis. *Journal of Experimental Medicine* 203(12): 2577–2587. <https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.20060244>
- Chiricozzi A, Krueger JG (2013) IL-17 targeted therapies for psoriasis. *Expert Opinion on Investigational Drugs* 22(8): 993–1005. <https://doi.org/10.1517/13543784.2013.806483>
- Chiricozzi A, Saraceno R, Chimenti MS, Guttman-Yassky E, Krueger JG (2014) Role of IL-23 in the pathogenesis of psoriasis: a novel potential therapeutic target? *Expert Opinion on Therapeutic Targets* 18(5): 513–525. <https://doi.org/10.1517/14728222.2014.889686>
- Colombel JF, Sendid B, Jouault T, Poulain D (2013) Secukinumab failure in Crohn's disease: the yeast connection? *Gut* 62(5): 800–801. <https://doi.org/10.1136/gutjnl-2012-304154>
- Craig S, Warren RB (2020) Ixekizumab for the treatment of psoriasis: up-to-date. *Expert Opinion on Biological Therapy* 20(6): 549–557. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14712598.2020.1729736>
- de Korte J, Sprangers MA, Mommers FM, Bos JD (2004) Quality of life in patients with psoriasis: a systematic literature review. *Journal of Investigative Dermatology Symposium Proceedings* 9(2): 140–147. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1087-0024.2003.09110.x>
- de Leon-Tabaldo A, Strawn D, Chang L, Cheng X, Greving C, Knight B, Sendekci J, Sherlock J, Modi NB, Kannan A, Fourie A (2024) P626 JNJ-77242113, an oral peptide selectively targeting the IL-23 receptor, demonstrates pharmacodynamic activity in rat and human colon tissue explants following oral dosing. *Journal of Crohn's and Colitis* 18: i1193–i1193. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ecco-jcc/jjad212.0756>
- Di Meglio P, Nestle FO (2010) The role of IL-23 in the immunopathogenesis of psoriasis. *F1000 Biology Reports* 2: 40. <https://doi.org/10.3410/B2-40>
- Dowlathshahi EA, van der Voort EAM, Arends LR, Nijsten T (2013) Markers of systemic inflammation in psoriasis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *British Journal of Dermatology* 169(2): 266–282. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.12355>
- Drucker DJ (2020) Advances in oral peptide therapeutics. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery* 19(4): 277–289. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41573-019-0053-0>
- Duvallet E, Semerano L, Assier E, Falgarone G, Boissier MC (2011) Interleukin-23: a key cytokine in inflammatory diseases. *Annals of Medicine* 43(7): 503–511. <https://doi.org/10.3109/07853890.2011.577093>
- Estevinho T, Lé AM, Torres T (2023) Deucravacitinib in the treatment of psoriasis. *Journal of Dermatological Treatment* 34(1): 2154122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546634.2022.2154122>
- Farahnik B, Beroukhim K, Zhu TH, Abrouk M, Nakamura M, Singh R, Lee K, Bhutani T, Koo J (2016) Ixekizumab for the treatment of psoriasis: A review of phase III trials. *Dermatology and Therapy* 6(1): 25–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13555-016-0102-0>
- Ferris LK, Bagel J, Huang YH, Pink AE, Tying SK, Kokolakis G, DeLozier AM, Li S, Shen YK, Iaconangelo C, Ota T, Bissonnette R (2025) FRONTIER-2: A phase 2b, long-term extension, dose-ranging study of oral JNJ-77242113 for the treatment of moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology* 92(3): 495–502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2024.10.076>
- Finlay AY, Coles EC (1995) The effect of severe psoriasis on the quality of life of 369 patients. *British Journal of Dermatology* 132(2): 236–244. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2133.1995.tb05019.x>
- Fotiadou C, Lazaridou E, Sotiriou E, Ioannides D (2018) Targeting IL-23 in psoriasis: current perspectives. *Psoriasis* 8: 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PTT.S98893>
- Fourie A, Cheng X, Chang L, Greving C, Patrick A, Knight B, Polidori D, Patch R, Bhandari A, Liu D, Huie K, Li S, Rodriguez M, Kannan A, Sherlock J, Modi N (2023) S1028 characterization of a first-in-class oral therapy selectively targeting the IL-23 pathway. *American Journal of Gastroenterology* 118(10S): S781–S781. <https://doi.org/10.14309/01.ajg.0000953752.29003.56>
- Fourie AM, Cheng X, Chang L, Greving C, Li X, Knight B, Polidori D, Patrick A, Bains T, Steele RJ, Allen SJ, Patch RJ, Sun C, Somani S, Bhandari A, Liu D, Huie K, Li S, Rodriguez MA, Modi NB (2024) JNJ-77242113, a highly potent, selective peptide targeting the IL-23 receptor, provides robust IL-23 pathway inhibition upon oral dosing in rats and humans. *Scientific Reports* 14(1): 17515. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-67371-5>
- Freitas E, Blauvelt A, Torres T (2021) Bimekizumab for the Treatment of Psoriasis. *Drugs* 81(15): 1751–1762. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40265-021-01612-z>
- Gaffen SL, Jain R, Garg AV, Cua DJ (2014) The IL-23–IL-17 immune axis: from mechanisms to therapeutic testing. *Nature Reviews Immunology* 14(9): 585–600. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nri3707>

- Girolomoni G, Mrowietz U, Paul C (2012) Psoriasis: rationale for targeting interleukin-17. *British Journal of Dermatology* 167(4): 717–724. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2133.2012.11099.x>
- Girolomoni G, Strohal R, Puig L, Bachelez H, Barker J, Boehncke WH, Prinz JC (2017) The role of IL-23 and the IL-23/TH17 immune axis in the pathogenesis and treatment of psoriasis. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 31(10): 1616–1626. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.14433>
- Gordon KB, Duffin KC, Bissonnette R, Prinz JC, Wasfi Y, Li S, Shen YK, Szapary P, Randazzo B, Reich K (2015) A phase 2 Trial of guselkumab versus adalimumab for plaque psoriasis. *New England Journal of Medicine* 373(2): 136–144. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1501646>
- Gordon KB, Foley P, Krueger JG, Pinter A, Reich K, Vender R, Vanvoorden V, Madden C, White K, Cioffi C, Blauvelt A (2021) Bimekizumab efficacy and safety in moderate to severe plaque psoriasis (BE READY): a multicentre, double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomised withdrawal phase 3 trial. *Lancet* 397(10273): 475–486. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)00126-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00126-4)
- Gordon KB, Strober B, Lebwohl M, Augustin M, Blauvelt A, Poulin Y, Papp KA, Sofen H, Puig L, Foley P, Ohtsuki M, Flack M, Geng Z, Gu Y, Valdes JM, Thompson EH, Bachelez H (2018) Efficacy and safety of risankizumab in moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis (UltIMMa-1 and UltIMMa-2): results from two double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled and ustekinumab-controlled phase 3 trials. *Lancet* 392(10148): 650–661. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31713-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31713-6)
- Griffiths CEM, Armstrong AW, Gudjonsson JE, Barker JNWN (2021) Psoriasis. *Lancet* 397(10281): 1301–1315. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)32549-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32549-6)
- Gu C, Yang J (2019) Risankizumab for the treatment of psoriasis. *Expert Review of Clinical Pharmacology* 12(9): 851–857. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17512433.2019.1657829>
- Hansel K, Zangrilli A, Bianchi L, Peris K, Chiricozzi A, Offidani A, Diotallevi F, Fargnoli MC, Esposito M, Amerio P, Gualdi G, Bianchi L, Stingeni L (2021) A multicenter study on effectiveness and safety of risankizumab in psoriasis: an Italian 16-week real-life experience during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 35(3): e169–e170. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.17003>
- Hansel K, Zangrilli A, Bianchi L, Peris K, Chiricozzi A, Offidani A, Diotallevi F, Fargnoli MC, Esposito M, Amerio P, Gualdi G, Bianchi L, Stingeni L (2022) A 52-week update of a multicentre real-life experience on effectiveness and safety of risankizumab in psoriasis. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 36(2): e111–e113. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.17656>
- Hohenberger M, Cardwell LA, Oussedik E, Feldman SR (2018) Interleukin-17 inhibition: role in psoriasis and inflammatory bowel disease. *Journal of Dermatological Treatment* 29(1): 13–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546634.2017.1329511>
- Huang X, Shentu H, He Y, Lai H, Xu C, Chen M, Zhu H (2023) Efficacy and safety of IL-23 inhibitors in the treatment of psoriatic arthritis: a meta-analysis based on randomized controlled trials. *Immunologic Research* 71(4): 505–515. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12026-023-09366-4>
- Huang YW, Tsai TF (2020) A drug safety evaluation of risankizumab for psoriasis. *Expert Opinion on Drug Safety* 19(4): 395–402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14740338.2020.1736034>
- Ko HC, Jwa SW, Song M, Kim MB, Kwon KS (2010) Clinical course of guttate psoriasis: long-term follow-up study. *Journal of Dermatology* 37(10): 894–899. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1346-8138.2010.00871.x>
- Kolli SS, Amin SD, Pona A, Cline A, Feldman SR (2018) Psychosocial impact of psoriasis: a review for dermatology residents. *Cutis* 102(5S): 21–25.
- Korn T, Bettelli E, Oukka M, Kuchroo VK (2009) IL-17 and Th17 cells. *Annual Review of Immunology* 27: 485–517. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.immunol.021908.132710>
- Korta A, Kula J, Gomułka K (2023) The role of IL-23 in the pathogenesis and therapy of inflammatory bowel disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24(12): 10172. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241210172>
- Kutwin M, Migdalska-Sęk M, Brzezińska-Lasota E, Zelga P, Woźniacka A (2021) An analysis of IL-10, IL-17A, IL-17RA, IL-23A and IL-23R expression and their correlation with clinical course in patients with psoriasis. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 10(24): 5834. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm10245834>
- Langley RG, Elewski BE, Lebwohl M, Reich K, Griffiths CEM, Papp K, Puig L, Nakagawa H, Spelman L, Sigurgeirsson B, Rivas E, Tsai TF, Wasel N, Tying S, Salko T, Hampele I, Notter M, Karpov A, Helou S, FIXTURE Study Group (2014) Secukinumab in plaque psoriasis—results of two phase 3 trials. *New England Journal of Medicine* 371(4): 326–338. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1314258>
- Leonardi CL, Kimball AB, Papp KA, Yeilding N, Guzzo C, Wang Y, Li S, Dooley LT, Gordon KB (2008) Efficacy and safety of ustekinumab, a human interleukin-12/23 monoclonal antibody, in patients with psoriasis: 76-week results from a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial (PHOENIX 1). *Lancet* 371(9625): 1665–1674. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(08\)60725-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(08)60725-4)
- Loft ND, Vaengebjerg S, Halling AS, Skov L, Egeberg A (2020) Adverse events with IL-17 and IL-23 inhibitors for psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis: a systematic review and meta-analysis of phase III studies. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 34(6): 1151–1160. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.16073>
- Lowes MA, Suárez-Fariñas M, Krueger JG (2014) Immunology of psoriasis. *Annual Review of Immunology* 32: 227–255. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-immunol-032713-120225>
- Lupardus PJ, Garcia KC (2008) The structure of interleukin-23 reveals the molecular basis of p40 subunit sharing with interleukin-12. *Journal of Molecular Biology* 382(4): 931–941. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2008.07.051>
- Ly K, Smith MP, Thibodeaux Q, Reddy V, Liao W, Bhutani T (2019) Anti IL-17 in psoriasis. *Expert Review of Clinical Immunology* 15(11): 1185–1194. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1744666X.2020.1679625>
- Mease PJ, Rahman P, Gottlieb AB, Kollmeier AP, Hsia EC, Xu XL, Sheng S, Agarwal P, Zhou B, Zhuang Y, van der Heijde D, McInnes IB, DISCOVER-2 Study Group (2020) Guselkumab in biologic-naïve patients with active psoriatic arthritis (DISCOVER-2): a double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled phase 3 trial. *Lancet* 395(10230): 1126–1136. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30263-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30263-4)
- Miossec P, Kolls JK (2012) Targeting IL-17 and TH17 cells in chronic inflammation. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery* 11(10): 763–776. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd3794>
- Naik PP (2022) Adverse effects of anti-interleukin-23 agents employed in patients with psoriasis: A systematic review. *Dermatology* 238(5): 886–896. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000524199>
- Nakamura M, Lee K, Jeon C, Sekhon S, Afifi L, Yan D, Lee K, Bhutani T (2017) Guselkumab for the treatment of psoriasis: A review of phase III trials. *Dermatology and Therapy* 7(3): 281–292. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13555-017-0187-0>

- Navarini AA, Burden AD, Capon F, Mrowietz U, Puig L, Köks S, Kingo K, Smith C, Barker JN, ERASPEN Network (2017) European consensus statement on phenotypes of pustular psoriasis. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 31(11): 1792–1799. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.14386>
- Nestle FO, Kaplan DH, Barker J (2009) Psoriasis. *New England Journal of Medicine* 361(5): 496–509. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra0804595>
- Nogueira M, Torres T (2019) Guselkumab for the treatment of psoriasis - evidence to date. *Drugs in Context* 8: 212594. <https://doi.org/10.7573/dic.212594>
- Oppmann B, Lesley R, Blom B, Timans JC, Xu Y, Hunte B, Vega F, Yu N, Wang J, Singh K, Zonin F, Vaisberg E, Churakova T, Liu M, Gorman D, Wagner J, Zurawski S, Liu Y, Abrams JS, Kastelein RA (2000) Novel p19 protein engages IL-12p40 to form a cytokine, IL-23, with biological activities similar as well as distinct from IL-12. *Immunity* 13(5): 715–725. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1074-7613\(00\)00070-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1074-7613(00)00070-4)
- Papp KA, Blauvelt A, Bukhalo M, Gooderham M, Krueger JG, Lacour JP, Menter A, Philipp S, Sofen H, Tyring S, Berner BR, Visvanathan S, Pamulapati C, Bennett N, Flack M, Scholl P, Padula SJ (2017) Risankizumab versus ustekinumab. *New England Journal of Medicine* 376(16): 1551–1560. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1607017>
- Papp KA, Langley RG, Lebwohl M, Krueger GG, Szapary P, Yeilding N, Guzzo C, Hsu MC, Wang Y, Li S, Dooley LT, Reich K (2008) Efficacy and safety of ustekinumab, a human interleukin-12/23 monoclonal antibody, in patients with psoriasis: 52-week results from a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial (PHOENIX 2). *Lancet* 371(9625): 1675–1684. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(08\)60726-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(08)60726-6)
- Papp KA, Langley RG, Sigurgeirsson B, Abe M, Baker DR, Konno P, Haemmerle S, Thurston HJ, Papavassilis C, Richards HB (2013) Efficacy and safety of secukinumab in the treatment of moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled phase II dose-ranging study. *British Journal of Dermatology* 168(2): 412–421. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.12110>
- Papp KA, Reich K, Blauvelt A, Kimball AB, Gooderham M, Tyring SK, Sinclair R, Thaci D, Li Q, Cichanowitz N, Green S, La Rosa C (2019) Efficacy of tildrakizumab for moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis: pooled analysis of three randomized controlled trials at weeks 12 and 28. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 33(6): 10981106. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.15400>
- Parham C, Chirica M, Timans JC, Vaisberg E, Travis M, Cheung J, Pflanz S, Zhang R, Singh KP, Vega F, To W, Wagner J, O'Farrell AM, McClanahan T, Zurawski S, Hannum C, Gorman D, Rennick DM, Kastelein RA, Moore KW (2002) A receptor for the heterodimeric cytokine IL-23 is composed of IL-12Rbeta1 and a novel cytokine receptor subunit, IL-23R. *Journal of Immunology* 168(11): 5699–5708. <https://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.168.11.5699>
- Perera GK, Di Meglio P, Nestle FO (2012) Psoriasis. *Annual Review of Pathology* 7: 385–422. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-pathol-011811-132448>
- Quatresooz P, Hermanns-Lê T, Piérard GE, Humbert P, Delvenne P, Piérard-Franchimont C (2012) Ustekinumab in psoriasis immunopathology with emphasis on the Th17-IL23 axis: a primer. *Journal of Biomedicine and Biotechnology* 2012: 147413. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/147413>
- Reddy M, Torres G, McCormick T, Marano C, Cooper K, Yeilding N, Wang Y, Pendley C, Prabhakar U, Wong J, Davis C, Xu S, Brodmerkel C (2010) Positive treatment effects of ustekinumab in psoriasis: analysis of lesional and systemic parameters. *Journal of Dermatology* 37(5): 413–425. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1346-8138.2010.00802.x>
- Reich K, Papp KA, Matheson RT, Tu JH, Bissonnette R, Bourcier M, Gratton D, Kunyetz RA, Poulin Y, Rosoph LA, Stingl G, Bauer WM, Salter JM, Falk TM, Blödorn-Schlicht NA, Hueber W, Sommer U, Schumacher MM, Peters T, Bleul CC (2015) Evidence that a neutrophil-keratinocyte crosstalk is an early target of IL-17A inhibition in psoriasis. *Experimental Dermatology* 24(7): 529–535. <https://doi.org/10.1111/exd.12710>
- Reich K, Puig L, Szepletowski JC, Paul C, Lacour JP, Tsianakas A, Sieder C, Rissler M, Pournara E, Orsenigo R (2020) Secukinumab dosing optimization in patients with moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis: results from the randomized, open-label OPTIMISE study. *British Journal of Dermatology* 182(2): 304–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.18143>
- Reich K, Warren RB, Iversen L, Puig L, Pau-Charles I, Igarashi A, Ohtsuki M, Falqués M, Harmut M, Rozzo S, Lebwohl MG, Cantrell W, Blauvelt A, Thaci D (2020) Long-term efficacy and safety of tildrakizumab for moderate-to-severe psoriasis: pooled analyses of two randomized phase III clinical trials (reSURFACE 1 and reSURFACE 2) through 148 weeks. *British Journal of Dermatology* 182(3): 605–617. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.18232>
- Reich K, Warren RB, Lebwohl M, Gooderham M, Strober B, Langley RG, Paul C, De Cuyper D, Vanvoorden V, Madden C, Cioffi C, Peterson L, Blauvelt A (2021) Bimekizumab versus Secukinumab in plaque psoriasis. *New England Journal of Medicine* 385(2): 142–152. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2102383>
- Rendon A, Schäkel K (2019) Psoriasis pathogenesis and treatment. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 20(6): 1475. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20061475>
- Rich P, Sigurgeirsson B, Thaci D, Ortonne JP, Paul C, Schopf RE, Morita A, Roseau K, Harfst E, Guettner A, Machacek M, Papavassilis C (2013) Secukinumab induction and maintenance therapy in moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase II regimen-finding study. *British Journal of Dermatology* 168(2): 402–411. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.12070>
- Riol-Blanco L, Ordovas-Montanes J, Perro M, Naval E, Thiriout A, Alvarez D, Paust S, Wood JN, von Andrian UH (2014) Nociceptive sensory neurons drive interleukin-23-mediated psoriasiform skin inflammation. *Nature* 510(7503): 157–161. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13199>
- Rivas Bejarano JJ, Valdecantos WC (2013) Psoriasis as autoinflammatory disease. *Dermatologic Clinics* 31(3): 445–460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.det.2013.04.009>
- Rosenberg AL, Akbik M, Kokikian N, Samman L, Munawar L, Wescott RM, Wu JJ (2025) Oral biologics: the new wave for treating psoriasis. *Cutis* 115(2): 59–60. <https://doi.org/10.12788/cutis.1169>
- Ruggiero A, Megna M, Fabbrocini G, Fornaro L, Villani A (2022) Drug safety evaluation of ixekizumab for psoriasis: a review of the current knowledge. *Expert Opinion on Drug Safety* 21(10): 1249–1257. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14740338.2022.2134855>
- Ruggiero A, Potestio L, Camela Snr E, Fabbrocini G, Megna M (2022) Bimekizumab for the treatment of psoriasis: a review of the current knowledge. *Psoriasis: Targets and Therapy* 12: 127–137. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PTT.S367744>
- Shu Y, Chen J, Ding Y, Zhang Q (2023) Adverse events with risankizumab in the real world: postmarketing pharmacovigilance assessment of the FDA adverse event reporting system. *Frontiers in Immunology* 14: 1169735. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2023.1169735>
- Sinclair R, Thirthar Palanivelu V (2019) Tildrakizumab for the treatment of psoriasis. *Expert Review of Clinical Immunology* 15(1): 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1744666X.2019.1544493>

- Singh RK, Lee KM, Ucmak D, Brodsky M, Atanelov Z, Farahnik B, Abrouk M, Nakamura M, Zhu TH, Liao W (2016) Erythrodermic psoriasis: pathophysiology and current treatment perspectives. *Psoriasis* 6: 93–104. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PTT.S101232>
- Sofen H, Smith S, Matheson RT, Leonardi CL, Calderon C, Brodmerkel C, Li K, Campbell K, Marciniak SJ, Wasfi Y, Wang Y, Szapary P, Krueger JG (2014) Guselkumab (an IL-23-specific mAb) demonstrates clinical and molecular response in patients with moderate-to-severe psoriasis. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 133(4): 1032–1040. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2014.01.025>
- Stein Gold L, Eyerich K, Merola JF, Torres J, Coates LC, Allegritti JR (2025) Oral peptide therapeutics as an emerging treatment modality in immune-mediated inflammatory diseases: A narrative review. *Advances in Therapy* 42(7): 3158–3172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12325-025-03213-8>
- Stritesky GL, Yeh N, Kaplan MH (2008) IL-23 promotes maintenance but not commitment to the Th17 lineage. *Journal of Immunology* 181(9): 5948–5955. <https://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.181.9.5948>
- Strober B, Menter A, Leonardi C, Gordon K, Lambert J, Puig L, Photowala H, Longcore M, Zhan T, Foley P (2020) Efficacy of risankizumab in patients with moderate-to-severe plaque psoriasis by baseline demographics, disease characteristics and prior biologic therapy: an integrated analysis of the phase III UltIMMa-1 and UltIMMa-2 studies. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 34(12): 2830–2838. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdv.16521>
- Syed YY (2017) Ixekizumab: A review in moderate to severe plaque psoriasis. *American Journal of Clinical Dermatology* 18(1): 147–158. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40257-017-0254-4>
- Ten Bergen LL, Petrovic A, Krogh Aarebrot A, Appel S (2020) The TNF/IL-23/IL-17 axis—Head-to-head trials comparing different biologics in psoriasis treatment. *Scandinavian Journal of Immunology* 92(4): e12946. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sji.12946>
- Torti DC, Feldman SR (2007) Interleukin-12, interleukin-23, and psoriasis: current prospects. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology* 57(6): 1059–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2007.07.016>
- van den Berg WB, McInnes IB (2013) Th17 cells and IL-17A—focus on immunopathogenesis and immunotherapeutics. *Seminars in Arthritis and Rheumatism* 43(2): 158–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semarthrit.2013.04.006>
- Vičić M, Kaštelan M, Brajac I, Sotošek V, Massari LP (2021) Current concepts of psoriasis immunopathogenesis. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 22(21): 11574. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms222111574>
- Watford WT, Hissong BD, Bream JH, Kanno Y, Muul L, O’Shea JJ (2004) Signaling by IL-12 and IL-23 and the immunoregulatory roles of STAT4. *Immunological Reviews* 202: 139–156. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0105-2896.2004.00211.x>
- Yeilding N, Szapary P, Brodmerkel C, Benson J, Plotnick M, Zhou H, Goyal K, Schenkel B, Giles-Komar J, Mascelli MA, Guzzo C (2012) Development of the IL-12/23 antagonist ustekinumab in psoriasis: past, present, and future perspectives—an update. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1263: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2012.06670.x>
- Zhou L, Wang Y, Wan Q, Wu F, Barbon J, Dunstan R, Gauld S, Konrad M, Leys L, McCarthy R, Namovic M, Nelson C, Overmeyer G, Perron D, Su Z, Wang L, Westmoreland S, Zhang J, Zhu R, Veldman G (2021) A non-clinical comparative study of IL-23 antibodies in psoriasis. *MABS* 13(1): 1964420. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19420862.2021.1964420>
- Zhu J, Yamane H, Paul WE (2010) Differentiation of effector CD4 T cell populations. *Annual Review of Immunology* 28: 445–489. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-immunol-030409-101212>

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Adhurim Bresa: Conceptualization, literature review, data analysis, writing—original draft preparation; Blina Kastrati: Literature review, data curation, writing—review and editing; Elira Berisha: Literature review, data curation, writing—review and editing; Ilir Besimi: Clinical interpretation, critical revision of the manuscript; Diamant Thaçi: Supervision, scientific validation, critical revision, and final approval of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

A. Bresa <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4377-6908>

B. Kastrati <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6885-9974>

E. Berisha <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0047-5899>

D. Thaçi <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8513-550X>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.